

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP3
Hybrid Grid Enabling Solutions

Deliverable D3.11
Control Layer Based Control Algorithms

Funding Instrument: Innovation Action
Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC
Call Topic: LC-SC3-ES-10-2020 - DC – AC/DC hybrid grid for a modular, resilient and high RES share grid development

Project Start: 1 October 2020
Project Duration: 48 months

Beneficiary in Charge: RWTH Aachen University

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.6102481](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6102481)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	HYPERRIDE
Project Number:	957788
Deliverable Number:	D3.11
Deliverable Full Title:	Control Layer Based Control Algorithms
Deliverable Short Title:	Hybrid Converter Control
Document Identifier:	HYPERRIDE-D311-HybridConverterControl-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	RWTH Aachen University
Report Version:	v1.3
Contractual Date:	31/03/2022
Report Submission Date:	08/06/2022
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Demonstrator
Lead Author(s):	Tim Karsten (RWTH Aachen)
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Keywords:	Converter Control Algorithm, Dual-Active Bridge, Active Front End, Modulation, Droop Control, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, HYPERRIDE, GA 957788
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> draft, <input type="checkbox"/> final, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
21/03/2022	v1.0	T. Karsten, J. Hu (RWTH Aachen)	First version for review
28/04/2022	v1.1	Staffan Norrga (SCIBREAK AB), D. Dujic (EPFL), E. Baron-Prada (AIT), G. Jambrich (AIT)	Review and improvement suggestions
04/05/2022	v1.2	T. Karsten (RWTH Aachen)	Update and improvements after review
08/06/2022	v1.3	G. Jambrich, T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version after Coordinator review

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List of Abbreviations

3L-NPC	Three Level Neutral Point Clamped
AC	Alternating Current
AC/DC	Alternating Current - Direct Current
ADCC	Asymmetrical Duty Cycle Control
AFE	Active Front End
ATB	Active Thermal Balancing
CWD	Center for Wind Power Drives
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DC	Direct Current
DoA	Description of Action
dq	direct-quadrature
DTC	Deadtime Compensation
ICC	Instantaneous Current Control
IEGT	Injection-Enhanced Gate Transistor
ISOP	Input Series Output Parallel
LV	Low Voltage
MARC	Modified Auxiliary Resonant Commutated Pole
MV	Medium Voltage
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PGS	Institute for Power Generation and Storage Systems
PI	Proportional-Integral
PLL	Phase-Locked Loop
PR	Proportional-Resonant
PWM	Pulse-Width Modulation
RMS	Root Mean Square
RWTH	RWTH Aachen University
SPS	Single Phase-Shift
SPWM	Sine-Triangle Pulse-Width Modulation
SST	Solid State Transformer
SVPWM	Space Vector Pulse-Width Modulation
TCM3	Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation
TCM3-Buck	Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation Buck Mode
TCM3-Boost	Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation Boost Mode
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
TZM3	Three-phase Trapezoidal-current Modulation
WP	Work Package
ZCS	Zero Current Switching
ZVS	Zero Voltage Switching

Executive Summary

The operation of a hybrid Alternating Current - Direct Current (AC/DC) grid relies on power electronic converters interfacing different sections of the grid. Each converter controls primarily voltage, current or transferred power. Together they achieve stable operation of the grid. Within this Work Package (WP) a layer based control approach for the converters in a hybrid grid has been proposed. As a reference system the HYPERRIDE demo site in Aachen was considered since the developed control algorithms are to be implemented there. Furthermore, it is important that the system can be operated under no communication, with the converter level control alone.

With these specifications in mind, control algorithms for different converter topologies were developed and implemented on hardware test setups. The existing GE 3L-NPC DAB and down-scaled 3L-NPC AFE testbenches at the demo site in Aachen, together with the for their operation already developed converter control algorithms, served as basis for the contributions of this deliverable. Those contributions include:

- Dead-time compensation of Dual Active Bridge (DAB);
- Active thermal balancing of DAB;
- Hardware implementation and verification of Three Level Neutral Point Clamped (3L-NPC) DAB modulation;
- Hardware implementation and verification of Instantaneous Current Control (ICC) of DAB;
- Hardware implementation and verification of 3L-NPC Active Front End (AFE) control;
- Down-scaled two-level DAB testbench.

The DAB topology is addressed because it couples Direct Current (DC) parts of the system and provides galvanic isolation. Moreover, it can reach high efficiencies with the proposed control algorithms. Basic operation characteristics of the DAB are covered with Single Phase-Shift (SPS) mode. Different modes of operation are presented to allow interfacing of energy storage systems and other types of loads and sources to the grid while maintaining soft-switching operation. A dead-time compensation is proposed to mitigate the effects of dead-times on operation of the DAB. In order to balance the thermal stress on the devices of the DAB, a balancing strategy is implemented. The control algorithms were tested and verified on a down-scaled hardware setup. An advanced three level modulation scheme and ICC for dynamic operation of the DAB were implemented and tested on the full-scale GE 3L-NPC DAB converter which is part of the demo site.

The coupling of Alternating Current (AC) and DC parts of the grid is achieved with AFE converters. The required control algorithms for current, voltage and power control are reviewed. They were implemented on a down-scaled 3L-NPC converter. Additionally, the balancing control of the split DC link of the 3L-NPC was experimentally verified.

An overview of the different proposed control layers is given. The features of each layer are discussed. Simulations were conducted to verify overall system stability under operation with converter level control since the HYPERRIDE demo site is currently under commissioning.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The activities and contributions of Task 3.11 "Hybrid Converter Control" are described and reported in this document. According to the Description of Action (DoA) the control algorithms necessary to control different converter topologies in a hybrid AC/DC grid were developed and reviewed. Measurements conducted on either full-scale or down-scaled hardware setups verify the proposed control methods. Different control layers are defined, with the converter level control as a basis to act upon. The control layer based control algorithms are to be implemented and tested on the HYPERRIDE demo site in Aachen as part of WP7.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This report has the following structure: Following the executive summary and the introduction, Section 2 gives an overview of the inspected converters and control layers. Control algorithms for the operation of DAB converters in a hybrid AC/DC grid are presented in Section 3. Section 4 explains AFE control algorithms and operation principles. The different control layers which are employed and their interconnection are described in Section 5 from a system perspective. Measurements acquired with hardware test setups demonstrate the implementation and performance of the proposed control algorithms. The deliverable is concluded in Section 6.

2 System Description

2.1 State of the Art

Three different demo sites are part of HYPERRIDE. The control algorithms developed within WP3.11 are designed for converters which are part of the demo site RWTH Aachen University (RWTH). As described in the DoA they are to be implemented and tested in the demo site as part of WP7. Therefore, this deliverable focuses on the system topology present in the Aachen demo site. Nevertheless, the control algorithms and layer based control approach can be applied to general hybrid AC/DC systems. In the following an overview of the system is given.

Figure 1: Schematic of RWTH Aachen demo site.

Figure 1 shows the available converters and their interconnection as inspected in this report. All converters are part of two geographically separated locations. Both are connected through the FEN DC grid. The majority of converters is located at the test hall of the Institute for Power Generation and Storage Systems (PGS). Three 50 Hz transformers allow connections to the AC grid at PGS. The Medium Voltage (MV) DC link is fed by a 5 MW three-phase 3L-NPC AFE and has a nominal voltage of 5 kV. Two DABs interface this DC link with the FEN DC grid. Marked with IGBT DAB3 is a 5 MW three-phase DAB converter which consists of two GE MV7000 3L-NPC converters and a medium-frequency transformer. The second DAB shown in parallel is a 5 MW IGCT based three-phase DAB converter with a Modified Auxiliary Resonant Commutated Pole (MARC) extension. The Low Voltage (LV) DC link is connected to the AC grid by a Solid State Transformer (SST) and serves as a connection point for various DC loads and sources as indicated. Two DAB converters couple the MV-DC and LV-DC links at PGS.

The FEN DC grid connects at its other end to the Center for Wind Power Drives (CWD). Here, a connection to the MV-AC grid is planned through an AFE and a 50 Hz transformer.

Since the RWTH HYPERRIDE demo site has not yet been commissioned some of the developments in this WP were implemented on down scaled test setups. Moreover, some of the control algorithms that are presented were developed in previous work and were implemented

and tested on hardware as part of this WP. Already existing control algorithms and hardware setups were:

- Basic modulation of two-level three-phase DAB;
- Asymmetrical duty cycle control of three-phase DAB;
- Three level three phase DAB modulation;
- Instantaneous Current Control (ICC) of DAB;
- Control algorithm for 3L-NPC AFE;
- GE 3L-NPC DAB testbench;
- Down-scaled 3L-NPC AFE testbench.

2.2 Contribution of the Deliverable

Developed as part of this WP in HYPERRIDE were the following control algorithms and hardware setups:

- Dead-time compensation of DAB;
- Active thermal balancing of DAB;
- Hardware implementation and verification of 3L-NPC DAB modulation;
- Hardware implementation and verification of ICC of DAB;
- Hardware implementation and verification of 3L-NPC AFE control;
- Down-scaled two-level DAB testbench.

Each converter has its own control hardware and communication interfaces. These components are fundamental requirements for the implementation of layer based control algorithms. Three control layers are proposed in the scope of this report:

- Converter level control;
- Inter-converter level control;
- System level control.

The three layers represent the different levels on which their control algorithms act. Moreover, each layer has its own communication. Converter level control implements the autonomous control actions of a single converter and acts as a platform to execute commands from higher control layers. It is based on the converter's own control hardware and sensors and therefore independent of communication to other layers or converters. Inter-converter level control describes control algorithms acting on multiple converters which share a common point of connection. It is enabled by local area communication between the converters which are involved. A system level control layer implements optimal power flow control algorithms and improves system availability and reliability. This requires a communication network connecting to every converter, sensor and actuator which is a part of the system level control.

3 DAB Control Algorithms

High-power bidirectional isolated DC-DC converters based on three-phase dual-active bridge (DAB) topologies serve as key enabling components to interface various energy sources and loads to the DC buses. Dependent on the application requirements, two-level and three-level variants of the DAB converter are employed to commission the DC part of the RWTH demo site. In this section, the fundamentals of the DAB converter will be first introduced, followed by dedicated control algorithms to ensure efficient and robust operation of the converters. Hardware set-ups of the DAB converters are commissioned to verify the developed control algorithms.

3.1 Fundamental Operation Principle

The three-phase DAB converter comprises two, three-phase converter bridges linked through a medium-frequency three-phase transformer as illustrated in Figure 2. Different from conventional Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) converters, the converters operate in the so-called square-wave mode with 50% duty cycle. The power flow in the DAB can be controlled by phase shifting the converter voltage waveform against each other, as shown in Figure 3. Thus, the power flow of the DAB converter can be controlled by the load angle φ between two converter bridges. For $0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{3}$, the transferred power is

$$P_{\text{SPS}} = \frac{dV_{\text{in}}^2}{\omega L_{\sigma}} \cdot \left(\frac{2\varphi}{3} - \frac{\varphi^2}{2\pi} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $d = \frac{N_{\text{tr}} V_{\text{out}}}{V_{\text{in}}}$, $\omega = 2\pi f$, f denotes the switching frequency, L_{σ} denotes the leakage inductance of the transformer.

Figure 2: Circuit diagram of the three-phase DAB converter.

This basic mode is referred to as single phase-shift (SPS) operation. SPS is widely used in DAB converters due to its buck and boost capability and Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) operation (De Doncker, Divan, & Kheraluwala, 1991). When ZVS is realised for the DAB converter, the system efficiency can be increased especially for the high-power applications. However, as depicted in Figure 4, the ZVS feature cannot be maintained when the converter operates in light-load conditions. Therefore, advanced modulation methods to extend the soft-switching range of the DAB converter are further investigated in the HYPERRIDE project.

Figure 3: SPS waveform of the DAB converter ($0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{3}$).

Figure 4: ZVS range of the DAB converter in the SPS mode.

3.2 Advanced Modulation Schemes to Extend the Soft-Switching Range

3.2.1 Asymmetrical Duty Cycle Control

As an interface converter to various energy sources and loads, the DAB converters often need to operate in light-load conditions with a large variation of the DC-link voltage. To tackle the constraint of narrow soft-switching range in the SPS mode, the asymmetrical duty cycle control (Asymmetrical Duty Cycle Control (ADCC)) method ((Hu et al., 2016)) is employed to the DAB converter, where the duty cycles of primary and secondary converter bridges D_p and D_s are variable. With D_p and D_s as additional degrees of freedom, triangular and trapezoidal waveform can be realised by the transformer winding currents, yielding Zero Current Switch-

ing (ZCS) operation of the DAB converter in light-load conditions. Depending on the voltage and the load, three operation modes in the ADCC method are defined, which are Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation Buck Mode (TCM3-Buck), Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation Boost Mode (TCM3-Boost) and Three-phase Trapezoidal-current Modulation (TZM3), as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Operation waveform of the three modulation modes in the ADCC method (Hu et al., 2016).

Table 1: Relationships of control parameters in the ADCC modulation method (Hu et al., 2016).

Mode	D_p	D_s
TCM3-Buck	$D_p(\varphi) = \frac{d}{1-d} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}$	$D_s(\varphi) = \frac{1}{1-d} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}$
TCM3-Boost	$D_p(\varphi) = \frac{d}{d-1} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}$	$D_s(\varphi) = \frac{1}{d-1} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}$
TZM3	$D_p(\varphi) = \frac{d}{1+d} \frac{2\pi - 3\varphi}{3\pi}$	$D_s(\varphi) = \frac{1}{1+d} \frac{2\pi - 3\varphi}{3\pi}$

Table 2: Transferred power of three modulation modes in the ADCC method (Hu et al., 2016).

Mode	Power
TCM3-Buck	$P = \frac{d^2 V_{in}^2 \varphi^2}{\pi^2 f L_{\sigma} (1-d)}$
TCM3-Boost	$P = \frac{d V_{in}^2 \varphi^2}{\pi^2 f L_{\sigma} (d-1)}$
TZM3	$P = \frac{d V_{in}^2 (6\pi\varphi(1+d^2) - 9\varphi^2(1+d+d^2) - \pi^2(1-d)^2)}{9\pi^2 f L_{\sigma} (1+d)^2}$

To realise the desired triangular and trapezoidal waveforms, the relationship between the control parameters φ , D_p and D_s in each operation mode is developed and summarised in Table 1. Furthermore, the transferred power of each ADCC mode can be calculated as a function of φ as given in Table 2.

The power transfer boundary of each modulation mode with respect to the voltage conversion ratio is depicted in Figure 6. The boundary of the TZM3 mode is interconnected to the boundaries of the TCM3-Buck and TCM3-Boost modes. Thus, three modulation modes of the ADCC method can be seamlessly combined, which significantly extends the soft-switching range in light-load conditions over a wide voltage range compared to the conventional SPS modulation. Moreover, due to the reduced duty cycles compared to the SPS modulation, the ADCC method

also presents a lower RMS current and lower peak flux density of the transformer in light-load conditions, leading to improved efficiency in light-load conditions.

Figure 6: Soft-switching range of the DAB converter in the ADCC and SPS mode (Hu et al., 2016).

3.2.2 Dead-time Compensation

When implementing the ADCC in the hardware set-up of HYPERRIDE, a dead time t_d is added between turn-off and turn-on of two switches in the same phase leg to prevent the phase leg from shoot-through. The output voltage of the phase leg in the dead-time interval is dependent on the polarity of the phase current. When a conducting switch is turned off, the anti-parallel diode of the complementary switch will conduct immediately. Consequently, the output voltage of the phase leg changes. With a reversed current polarity, the current flows through the anti-parallel diode when the switch is turned off, and the output voltage stays the same after turning off. The output voltage changes until the complementary switch turns on after the dead time or when the current polarity reverses.

Explained by aforementioned mechanism, the effective duty cycles D_p , D_s and the load angle φ of the generated voltages may differ from those in the pre-calculated switching pattern, which results in a deviated current waveform as shown in Figure 7.

The deviated voltage and current waveform will have two major impacts on the converter operation:

- Deviation in the transferred power from the reference value;
- Violation of the soft-switching condition.

Moreover, due to the inherently small duty cycles in a range of $[0, 1/3]$, the dead-time effect is more serious for the ADCC modes under light-load conditions with a large voltage variation. Although the deviated transferred power can be eventually compensated by the closed-loop control, the ZCS operation of the ADCC method has to be ensured by the Dead-time Compensation (DTC) in an open-loop manner.

In the aforementioned triangular and trapezoidal current waveform, the phase current is in the same polarity with the AC voltages. Thus, the primary AC voltage changes at the switching instants of the top switches, while the secondary AC voltage changes at the switching instants of the bottom switches. Therefore, a simple DTC method is proposed in the HYPERRIDE project to maintain the desired ZCS current waveform. The top switches in the primary bridge and the bottom switches in the secondary bridge should switch at the pre-calculated switching

Figure 7: Dead-time effect on the ADCC waveform of the DAB converter.

instants, respectively, as shown in Figure 8. Additionally, a zero-current zero-voltage interval with a duration of t_d is inserted at the end of each one third of the switching period to avoid interference to the other phases. Thereby, the dead-time effect on the ADCC modes can be avoided to ensure the ZCS operation. The proposed DTC method apply for both the Three-phase Triangular-current Modulation (TCM3) and TZM3 modes. Considering the fact that the dead time is usually implemented as a delay of the turn-on instants for the switches, the proposed DTC method can be equally realised by modifying the pre-calculated control parameters D_p , D_s and φ as given in Table 3.

Figure 8: Dead-time compensation scheme on the ADCC waveform of the DAB converter.

Table 3: Modified Control Parameters of the ADCC with the DTC method.

	TCM3-Buck	TCM3-Boost	TZM3
$D_{p,DTC}$	$D_p + ft_d$	$D_p + ft_d$	$D_p + ft_d$
$D_{s,DTC}$	D_s	D_s	$D_s - ft_d$
φ_{DTC}	$\varphi + 2\pi ft_d$	$\varphi + 2\pi ft_d$	$\varphi + 2\pi ft_d$

3.2.3 Active Thermal Balancing Strategy

Although the soft-switching characteristics and reduced Root Mean Square (RMS) current of the ADCC method improve the light-load efficiency for a wide voltage range operation, the power loss is unevenly distributed between the top and bottom devices in the same half bridge due to the asymmetrical duty cycles. As shown in Figure 9(a), taking the TZM3 mode as an example, it is obvious that the conducting current and conduction time of the top and bottom devices in the same half bridge vary from each other significantly. Besides, the turn-off current is also different for the top and bottom switches. The top switches of the primary bridge are turned off at the positive peak current, while the bottom switches realise ZCS turn-off. Similar asymmetrical characteristics are also found for the devices of the secondary bridge. Since the power semiconductor devices are normally packed in half bridge or even three-phase power modules, uneven power-loss distribution results in imbalanced junction temperatures in the devices, which may reduce the reliability of the semiconductor devices as well as the converter system.

To address the thermal imbalance in the ADCC method, an Active Thermal Balancing (ATB) strategy is developed in the HYPERRIDE project, which utilises the opposite voltage vectors in the three-phase converter. For each switching cycle of the ADCC method with $0 \leq D \leq 1/3$, an alternative switching cycle with $2/3 \leq D \leq 1$ can be identified by simply swapping the gate signals between the top and bottom devices, as shown in Figure 9(b). Since the same control parameters are utilised in the alternative switching cycle, the trapezoidal current waveform can still be realised, but with reversed polarity. Thus, compared to the normal switching cycle, the alternative switching cycle can transfer the same power. Due to the swapped duty cycles between the top and bottom devices in the alternative cycles, the power losses of the top and bottom devices are also swapped. Therefore, the power loss and the thermal stress of the semiconductor devices can be balanced effectively with the proposed ATB method, without affecting the transferred power and soft-switching operation.

3.2.4 Demonstration of the Developed Control Algorithm

Since the full-scale two-level DAB converter is still under commissioning in WP7, a down-scaled test set-up is designed to demonstrate the developed DAB control algorithm. As shown in Figure 10, the test set-up consists of two DAB converters connected in parallel for the power circulation. The parameters of the DAB prototype are given in Table 4. The control algorithm is implemented on a AiXControl XRS7070 real-time controller. The input DC link is fed in by a programmable DC source, and a LMG500 high-precision power analyser is employed for evaluating the energy efficiency.

Firstly, the ADCC TCM3-Buck mode is validated at $U_s = 64$ V and the reference power $P_{ref} = 75$ W. As depicted in Figure 11, the DTC method effectively corrects the power deviation caused by the dead time from $P_{meas} = 54.1$ W to $P_{meas} = 73.2$ W, and realises the desired ZCS current

Figure 9: Conducting devices of the primary and secondary bridge in the TZM3 mode (S for switch, D for diode). (a) Normal cycle with $0 \leq D_p, D_p \leq 1/3$, (b) Alternative cycle with $2/3 \leq D_p, D_p \leq 1$.

Figure 10: Photograph of the DAB converter set-up.

waveform. Similarly, the voltage and current waveforms of the ADCC TCM3-Boost mode are measured at $U_s = 96\text{ V}$ and $P_{ref} = 75\text{ W}$ as shown in Figure 12. In this case, the dead time causes more distortions in the current waveform and a larger power deviation ($P_{meas} = 5.6\text{ W}$), which are also effectively compensated by the DTC. Furthermore, the measurement is also performed for the TZM3 mode at $U_s = 80\text{ V}$ and $P_{ref} = 225\text{ W}$. As presented in Figure 13(a), a distorted triangular current waveform can be observed due to the dead time. Although the distortion of the current waveform is not as significant as the TCM3-Boost mode, the ZCS soft-

Table 4: Specifications of the designed DAB converter set-up.

Description	Variable	Value
Fixed primary dc voltage	$U_{p,nom}$	80 V
Nominal secondary dc voltage	$U_{s,nom}$	80 V
Nominal power	P_{nom}	600 W
Primary dc-link capacitance	C_{pDC}	0.99 mF
Secondary dc-link capacitance	C_{sDC}	0.99 mF
On-state resistance of MOSFET	R_{ds}	30 m Ω
Transformer turns ratio	N_{tr}	1
Transformer leakage inductance	L_{σ}	29 μ H
Transformer winding resistance	R_w	129 m Ω
Switching frequency	f	20 kHz
Dead time	t_d	1 μ s

switching condition is not realised. An input power of $P_{meas} = 173.8$ W is measured in this condition. On the other hand, with the DTC method, a desired trapezoidal current waveform with ZCS is realised as shown in Figure 13(b), which transfers an actual power of $P_{meas} = 219.5$ W. The aforementioned results have validated the effectiveness of the ADCC modulation schemes with the DTC method.

Figure 11: Measured waveform of ADCC TCM3-Buck mode at $U_s = 64$ V and $P_{ref} = 75$ W. (a) Without DTC ($P_{meas} = 54.1$ W), (b) With DTC ($P_{meas} = 73.2$ W).

Furthermore, the efficiency of the three-phase DAB converter prototype is measured and scanned over a wide voltage range at different load conditions. The secondary dc-link voltage varies from $U_s = 56$ V to $U_s = 104$ V, and the load varies from $P_{ref} = 75$ W to $P_{ref} = 600$ W. As shown in Figure 14, by comparing all the operation conditions, it is obvious that the efficiency of the SPS modulation is highly dependent on the operation condition. At $d = 1$, the SPS modulation presents the maximum efficiency up to 98.0%, which is slightly higher than the ADCC method (97.7%). However, with an increased voltage variation, due to the hard-switching operation and increased RMS current, the efficiency of the SPS modulation decreases significantly, especially under light-load conditions. As shown in Figure 14(c), the lowest efficiency of the

Figure 12: Measured waveform of ADCC TCM3-Buck mode at $U_s = 96\text{ V}$ and $P_{\text{ref}} = 75\text{ W}$. (a) Without DTC ($P_{\text{meas}} = 5.6\text{ W}$), (b) With DTC ($P_{\text{meas}} = 78\text{ W}$).

Figure 13: Measured waveform of ADCC TCM3-Buck mode at $U_s = 80\text{ V}$ and $P_{\text{ref}} = 225\text{ W}$. (a) Without DTC ($P_{\text{meas}} = 173.8\text{ W}$), (b) With DTC ($P_{\text{meas}} = 219.5\text{ W}$).

SPS modulation occurs at $U_s = 104\text{ V}$ and $P_{\text{ref}} = 75\text{ W}$ with 74.9%, whereas the efficiency of the ADCC method is in a significantly lower dependency of the voltage variation and load conditions. In the scanned operation range, the efficiency of the ADCC method is maintained within a narrow range of 94.8% to 97.7%. The light-load efficiency of the built DAB converter prototype is improved by up to 19.9%. Therefore, the hybrid modulation strategy, which utilises the ADCC method under light-load conditions and the SPS under medium-to-heavy load conditions, improves the average efficiency over a wide operation range. When the system scales up to a full-size MV DAB converter, the efficiency improvement by using the ADCC modulation still needs to be validated. However, due to the realisation of combined ZVS turn-on and ZCS turn-off as well as reduced RMS current, the light-load efficiency of the full-scaled converter with a large voltage variation is also expected to increase considerably.

The proposed ATB method is also implemented and verified on the test set-up. With the continuous mode-swapping operation, the transformer currents and output DC current are shown in Figure 15(a), which coincide well with the analysis and simulation. It is also verified in Fig-

Figure 14: Comparison of the measured efficiency between the SPS and ADCC methods at different primary dc-link voltages and load conditions. (a) $U_s = 64$ V. (b) $U_s = 96$ V. (c) $P_{ref} = 75$ W and 150 W.

ure 15(b) that a switch-over from the normal switching cycle to the alternative switching cycle will not change the output DC current of the three-phase DAB converter. Moreover, the thermal images of the top and bottom switches in a phase leg are captured under different operation scenarios. As shown in Figure 15(c-e), when the normal and the alternative switching cycles are swapped periodically, the case temperatures of the top and bottom switches become balanced, and the maximum case temperature is also reduced. This is beneficial for reducing the thermal cycle and improving the reliability of the semiconductor devices.

In the end, a closed-loop control is implemented for the proposed ADCC method to verify the transient performance with a load step change from 150 W to 250 W in the ADCC mode at at $U_s = 80$ V. It is shown in Figure 16 that the secondary-side DC voltage is well regulated, and the transformer currents of the ADCC modulation remain stable in the transient conditions.

Figure 15: Measurement results of the ATB method in the TZM3 mode at $U_s = 64 \text{ V}$ and $P_{\text{ref}} = 200 \text{ W}$. (a) Transformer currents and output dc current with the continuous mode-swapping between the normal and the alternative switching cycle. (b) Transformer currents and output dc current with a switch-over between the normal switching cycle and alternative switching cycle. (c) Captured thermal image of one primary-side phase leg by applying only the normal switching cycle. (d) Captured thermal image of one primary-side phase leg by applying only the alternative switching cycle. (e) Captured thermal image of one primary-side phase leg with the continuous mode-swapping between the normal and the alternative switching cycle.

3.3 5 MW Three Level DAB

Part of the RWTH demo site in HYPERRIDE is a 5 MW, three phase 3L-NPC DAB converter. Figure 18 shows one of the 3L-NPC phase legs. The converter features a medium-frequency transformer designed for an operation frequency of 1 kHz. A view of the converter is shown in

Figure 16: Closed-loop load transient of the three-phase DAB converter from 150W to 250W in the ADCC mode at $U_s = 80\text{V}$.

Figure 17. As power electronic switches Injection-Enhanced Gate Transistor (IEGT)s are used. How the converter is incorporated into the demo site is visualized in Figure 1. It is part of the test bench including the MV AFE at PGS.

The SPS modulation is the basis for more advanced modulation schemes of three phase DABs and can also be applied to a 3L-NPC DAB. In each phase leg the upper switches are switched with 50% duty cycle and the lower switches are switched complementary to the upper ones. Between each phase leg is a 120° phase-shift to account for the three phases. The transferred power is controlled through adjustment of the phase-shift between primary and secondary side.

The three level topology offers more degrees of freedom in the modulation of the DAB compared to a two level topology. These degrees of freedom can be used for midpoint balancing and optimization of star-point voltage harmonics according to an advanced modulation scheme proposed in (Joebges et al., 2018). Based on the SPS operation, in the three level DAB additional parameters k_1 and k_2 define the duty cycle of the outer switches in each 3L-NPC phase leg of primary and secondary side. Equation (2) - Equation (3) define the modulation parameter Δ_k based on the difference of k_1 and k_2 (Joebges et al., 2018). The turn-on of the outer low-side switches and turn-off of the inner high-side switches is delayed by a second control parameter λ (Joebges et al., 2018). Adjustments of these parameters allow for control of the average midpoint current per switching period. Therefore, a balancing of the midpoint is possi-

Figure 17: View of the 5 MW medium-frequency three-level DAB converter.

Figure 18: Simplified schematic of a 3L-NPC phase leg.

ble for asymmetrical loading on one side of the DAB. The difference of the duty cycles of the outer switches between primary and secondary side allows for optimization of operation.

$$\Delta_k = (k_2 - k_1) \cdot \pi \quad (2)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{5}{12} - \frac{\Delta_k}{2\pi} \tag{3}$$

$$k_2 = \frac{5}{12} + \frac{\Delta_k}{2\pi} \tag{4}$$

Figure 19: Impact of modulation parameters on secondary side phase voltage (Joebges et al., 2018).

Figure 20: Impact of modulation parameters on phase currents and midpoint current (Joebges et al., 2018).

A detailed analysis and description are beyond the scope of this deliverable but can be found in (Joebges et al., 2018). This advanced modulation scheme was implemented on the three level three phase DAB at the RWTH demo site.

Part of the dynamic control implemented on the converter is an ICC. Its purpose is to prevent DC bias in transformer currents as consequences of dynamic changes in phase-shift of the DAB. At the same time ICC can minimize transients of transformer and DC link currents

during dynamic operation. Figure 21 shows the $\alpha\beta$ equivalent circuit of a three phase transformer, neglecting its winding resistance. Each switching state of primary and secondary side corresponds to one of six space vectors in the $\alpha\beta$ frame as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 21: Simplified $\alpha\beta$ equivalent circuit of DAB transformer.

Figure 22: Space vector representation of DAB switching states.

If SPS operation is assumed, the transitions between the different switching states are known for given operating points. Therefore, the transformer current trajectory can be determined in $\alpha\beta$ frame. Using the $\alpha\beta$ representation, different ICC methods can be analysed regarding DC bias and overshoot (Engel et al., 2013). Figure 24 and Figure 25 show the phase current trajectories in the $\alpha\beta$ frame for changes of the phase-shift φ (Engel et al., 2013). The improvement in dynamic operation with ICC is visible in the current trajectories. No overshoots or DC bias are generated, in contrast to operation without ICC. Using ICC, if the phase-shift is supposed to change from φ_1 to φ_2 , at first only half of the change is applied according to Equation (5). Afterwards, in an intermediate step of the switching period the final phase-shift φ_2 is applied. This way, steady-state is reached within one half of the switching period and no overshoots in current occur. Figure 23 shows within a simplified control schematic of the DAB where the ICC block is placed. The output of the current control is the phase-shift between primary and secondary side of the DAB. Before the phase-shift is applied to the modulator unit it is passed through the ICC block.

$$\varphi_{\text{half}} = \frac{\varphi_1 + \varphi_2}{2} \quad (5)$$

A detailed analysis and description of the ICC is beyond the scope of this deliverable but can be found in (Engel, Soltau, Stagge, & De Doncker, 2014).

Figure 23: Position of ICC within DAB control schematic.

Figure 24: $\alpha\beta$ phase current trajectory without ICC under load angle change. (a) No sign change. (b) Sign change of load angle. (Engel et al., 2013).

Figure 25: $\alpha\beta$ phase current trajectory with ICC under load angle change. (a) No sign change. (b) Sign change of load angle. (Engel et al., 2013).

In the following measurements the 5 MW 3L-NPC DAB was operated under ICC including instantaneous flux control based on (Hu, Cui, Wang, & De Doncker, 2020).

Figure 26 shows two phase voltages of the primary side and the first phase voltage of the secondary side during dynamic operation. A DC link voltage of 1500 V was applied and the converter was operated at a switching frequency of 1 kHz. At $t = 0.8\text{s}$ the phase-shift command between primary and secondary side is changed from 0° to 8° . The ICC according to Equation (5) is applied and the actual phase angle is updated in two steps. The intermediate

Figure 26: Primary and secondary phase voltages during dynamic operation under ICC.

Figure 27: Primary phase currents during dynamic operation under ICC.

step is clearly visible in Figure 27 in the first phase current. It can be observed how both shown phase currents change in amplitude and reach their steady-state at $t = 1.8$ s. No overshoot in current is visible. Steady-state is reached after half the switching period.

4 AFE Control Algorithms

AC and DC grids in future energy systems are interconnected by AFEs if controlled, bidirectional power flow is desired. A dynamic control of transferred power is necessary while maintaining high power quality. In the following the basic structures implementing such a control are presented for grid tied AFEs. The application in microgrids involving islanding operation will not be considered in the following as it does not apply to the HYPERRIDE RWTH demo site. Section 4.2 describes advanced control features specific to the 3L-NPC topology.

4.1 Basic Control

Grid tied AFEs can be controlled to either transfer power according to given set-points or to regulate their DC link voltage. Both cases require a similar control structure and sensors. A synchronisation to the AC grid is necessary for the decoupled control of active and reactive power. This can be achieved by either controlling the grid currents in a synchronous reference frame with a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller and employing a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) or by using a Proportional-Resonant (PR) controller. Output of the controller is a voltage command which is passed to the modulator of the converter. The two basic modulation techniques which can be used are Sine-Triangle Pulse-Width Modulation (SPWM) and Space Vector Pulse-Width Modulation (SVPWM). In order to achieve damping of harmonics and to smooth the AC currents of the AFE, a filter connects the power electronic switches to the AC grid. According to grid codes and application requirements either an L or an LCL filter is chosen.

Considered in the work of WP3.11 was a 3L-NPC AFE. Its electrical schematic is shown in Figure 28. Each converter leg can generate an AC output voltage of $\pm V_{DC}/2$ and zero with respect to the midpoint of the AFE. The addition of the zero state allows lower current harmonics compared to a two-level AFE. Especially in high-power, low switching frequency converters this factor is relevant.

Figure 28: Schematic of the 3L-NPC AFE.

Figure 29 shows a schematic of the AFE current control developed and demonstrated within WP3.11. A PI controller is chosen for the control structure. Therefore, all quantities are transformed to the direct-quadrature (dq) reference frame with the Park transformation. Required input parameter of the transformation is the grid voltage angle θ . It is determined by the PLL

block which transforms the three phase grid voltage to the dq frame and employs a PI controller and an integrator to regulate the q component of the measured grid voltage to zero. The grid voltage angle θ determined by the PLL is fed to all Park transformation blocks.

Figure 29: Schematic of the current control loop.

Input to the PI controller of the current loop is the deviation between reference current and measured AC current transformed to dq frame. Its output variable is the PWM voltage command v_{pwm} . In the dq frame all quantities are DC quantities allowing the PI controller to eliminate any steady-state error. Its behavior is described by Equation (6). However, a cross coupling between d- and q-component of the current occurs. A decoupling is implemented through a feedforward of the d-component current to the q-component controller and the other way around. In this feedforward path each component is scaled with a gain equal to the product of filter inductance and angular frequency of the grid. If the ohmic resistance between converter output and Point of Common Coupling (PCC) is not negligible and can be estimated with sufficient precision, a second feedforward path is added to the current control. The d and q current components are scaled with the estimated resistance value and added to the output voltage according to Equation (7). The influence of the grid voltage can be decoupled by adding the measured AC grid side voltage components to the current control output. Since an LCL filter is employed the AC side capacitor current is fed back, scaled with a damping factor k_{dmp} and added to the current control output. This prevents interaction between the converter and the resonance of the LCL filter. Equation (8) shows the composition of the PWM voltage command v_{pwm} .

$$\underline{v}_{dq,i} = (\underline{i}_{dq,ref} - \underline{i}_{dq,grid}) \cdot \left(k_p + \frac{k_i}{s}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\underline{v}_{dq,R} = \underline{i}_{dq,ref} \cdot R_{grid} \quad (7)$$

$$\underline{v}_{pwm} = \underline{v}_{dq,i} + \underline{v}_{d,grid} + \underline{v}_{dq,R} + j\omega L_{grid} \cdot \underline{i}_{dq,ref} + \underline{i}_{dq,C} \cdot k_{dmp} \quad (8)$$

A voltage control is realised by adding an outer control loop to the so far discussed current control loop. Its schematic is shown in Figure 30. Equation (9) describes the control function. Analog to the current control a PI controller regulates the DC link voltage. Its output variable however is the DC current which has to be generated by the converter in order to regulate the DC link voltage. A transformation of this output variable to the AC side of the converter is necessary since the current controller regulates the AC currents. This is achieved by assuming equal power flows between AC and DC side of the AFE. The transformation of desired DC current to AC grid current in dq frame is achieved through division and multiplication with the corresponding voltages according to Equation (10). Depending on the convention chosen in the Park transformation a factoring of $3/2$ has to be applied.

$$\underline{i}_{d,ref} = ((v_{DC,ref} - v_{DC}) \cdot (k_p + \frac{k_i}{s}) + i_{load}) \cdot k_{tr} \quad (9)$$

$$k_{tr} = \frac{v_{DC}}{v_{d,grid}} \cdot 1.5 \quad (10)$$

If a current sensor is installed at the DC side of the converter the DC output current can be decoupled to optimise dynamic control performance of the voltage controller. The d-component current reference which is then fed to the current controller consists of the current command of the voltage control. It is directly related to the active power drawn from or sourced to the AC grid. The q-component of the current reference is used to control the reactive power supplied to the AC grid. It should be noted that the decoupling of active and reactive power and their assignment to d- and q-component of the current is only possible if the q-component of the grid voltage is regulated to be zero by the PLL.

Figure 30: Schematic of the voltage control loop.

The sensors required for the implemented control are AC grid side voltage and current sensors, DC link voltage sensor and optionally DC load current sensors. Their measurement signals or processed measurement signals can be made available by the converter's control system to the inter-converter level control layer or the system level control.

The modulation of the PWM voltage commands given by the controller is implemented with space vector modulation. Each valid switching state of the AFE corresponds to one vector in the $\alpha\beta$ frame. The vectors are obtained by applying the Clark transformation to the three phase voltages at the AC converter terminals for each switching state. A total of 27 valid switching states exist, yielding a total of six different large, six different medium sized and six different small sized space vectors as shown in Figure 31. Each three digit number represents one unique switching state of the converter. Every voltage reference within the hexagon can be

synthesised by addition of different space vectors. The maximum AC phase voltage amplitude that can be generated without over-modulation is $\frac{2}{3}V_{DC} \cdot \cos(\pi/6)$. Different approaches exist implementing either optimisation of switching losses or optimisation of grid current Total Harmonic Distortion (THD). Here, a five segment switching function is used, consisting of 3 different vectors. Compared to seven or nine segment switching patterns this allows a compromise between THD performance and switching losses. Figure 32 shows one of the six segments of the hexagon in Figure 31. The voltage reference is generated by applying space vectors that are adjacent to it for part of the switching period. If for example the reference vector lies within the first triangle, two small size space vectors and one zero vector are used in the switching pattern. Equation (11) and Equation (12) describes the relation between voltage reference and on-times of the switching states. Symmetry of the switching pattern is achieved by dividing the on-times of the first two switching states in half. They are repeated in reverse order after the third switching state, thus implementing a five step switching pattern according to Equation (13).

Figure 31: Visualization of 3L-NPC space vectors.

$$\underline{v}_{\text{ref}} = \underline{v}_1 \cdot t_1 + \underline{v}_2 \cdot t_2 + \underline{v}_3 \cdot t_3 \quad (11)$$

$$T_{\text{sw}} = t_1 + t_2 + t_3 \quad (12)$$

$$\underline{v}_{\text{ref}} = \underline{v}_1 \cdot \frac{t_1}{2} + \underline{v}_2 \cdot \frac{t_2}{2} + \underline{v}_3 \cdot t_3 + \underline{v}_2 \cdot \frac{t_2}{2} + \underline{v}_1 \cdot \frac{t_1}{2} \quad (13)$$

Figure 32: Visualisation of one hexagon segment for 3L-NPC SVPWM.

4.2 Additional Control Features

The main advantages of a multilevel topology compared to a two level topology are reduced grid current harmonic content and lower required blocking voltage rating of the power electronic switches. In the case of the 3L-NPC the DC link is split into two parts and requires a balanced voltage for proper operation. Self-balancing capability of the DC link depends on the filter dimensioning, switching frequency and control bandwidth of the converter. In most cases active balancing of the midpoint voltage is required. Different approaches can be employed depending on the modulation scheme of the converter. SPWM allows for the implementation of a common-mode voltage injection. In this case a PI controller forms a common-mode voltage command which is added to the voltage command of the current control loop output of the AFE. The injected common-mode voltage causes a current to flow into the midpoint of the DC link contributing to its balancing.

Since the proposed AFE control operates with SVPWM a balancing control based on the choice of switching patterns is chosen. Input variable for the control is the difference voltage between both DC link capacitors. The output of a hysteresis controller is switched as soon as the midpoint voltage reaches a chosen threshold. Depending on the sign of the midpoint voltage the switching pattern is adjusted to control the midpoint current. The small and medium size space vectors of the 3L-NPC contribute to the midpoint current. Every small size space vector has two redundant switching states with opposite effect on the midpoint current. The direction of the neutral point current is also influenced by the direction of active power flow of the converter. Therefore, the choice of switching states in the implemented five segment switching pattern is controlled by the midpoint hysteresis controller and depends on the sign of transferred power and midpoint voltage.

4.3 Hardware Setup and Measurements

The presented controls were implemented on a down scaled hardware setup to allow comprehensive testing under different operating conditions. Figure 33 shows a view of the used Semikron 3L-NPC. An overview of the assembled test setup is shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35. The converter was operated at a switching frequency of 20 kHz while the PWM update frequency was limited to 5 kHz. This was done to allow a smaller sized LCL filter while emu-

lating the control behavior of lower switching frequency, high power converters. Connection to the LV AC grid was done with an autotransformer set to an output line-to-line voltage of 200 V. Additionally, a transformer with a voltage ratio of 1 : 1 was used in order to provide galvanic isolation. On the DC side resistors were connected as loads.

Figure 33: View of employed converter.

Figure 34: View of assembled setup.

Figure 36 shows the AC grid currents of the AFE. A step input from 2 A to 4 A is applied to the d-component input of the current control loop at $t = 0.05$ s. The q-component reference is kept at zero. Therefore, only active power is transferred by the AFE. A fast response with short overshoot in the grid currents can be seen. Overall, the function of the current control loop is satisfactory with the proposed control structure. However, the measurements show some increased harmonic content in the grid currents. This is due to the fact that an autotransformer with relatively low output voltage was used and the grid voltage had harmonic content. Additionally, the dimensioning of the LCL filter components was not optimised for the given test

Figure 35: View of second cabinet.

setup and parameters.

Figure 36: AFE grid current transients under current control.

A test of the voltage control was conducted for an unbalanced DC load. The DC link voltage and current of the first phase are shown in Figure 37 during the startup procedure. As soon as the DC voltage reaches 280 V the AFE actively controls the charging of the DC link by ramping up the voltage reference. At the time instant $t = 1.5\text{ s}$ the load resistors are connected to the DC link. A power of 54 W and 36 W are drawn from the top and bottom half DC link respectively. The split DC link voltages are plotted in Figure 38. It can be observed that the balancing control prevents any imbalance of the split DC link during operation, even under unbalanced loading.

Figure 37: AFE DC link voltage and phase current.

Figure 38: AFE DC link and neutral point voltages.

5 Layered Control Algorithms and System Perspective

5.1 Motivation and Benefits

Hybrid AC/DC power systems require more complex control than classical AC systems. Centralised and decentralised approaches are discussed in literature for the implementation of all required control. Safety of operation and reliability as well as ruggedness under cyber-attacks play an important role. In the scope of this report a layer based control architecture is proposed. Each control layer can operate without the next higher level layer but requires the next lower level layer for implementation of its own control. Corresponding to each layer a communication layer is required. With this structure the system stays operational even under cyber-attacks or other faults in higher level layers. The converter level control layer works autonomously, solely based on each converter's own control hardware and measurement devices.

Demonstrations of full-scale system behavior and control implementation for the connection of multiple converters will be part of WP7. Therefore, simulation results generated in PLECS are part of this deliverable.

Since optimum power flow algorithm and overall system control development are not part of D3.11 only an overview of the system control layer is given in the following.

An overall economic and reliable operation of the system can be ensured with a system level control layer. On this layer an optimum power flow algorithm can act to reconfigure the grid, dispatch energy and give set-points to converters. A communication network spanning all controlled converters is required for this layer. The different measurements from the converters can be collected and control commands transmitted this way. Since the time frame of optimum power flow control is greater than that of immediate converter control, the measurement data and control commands are transmitted in correspondingly larger time steps. All sensors installed in converters as part of the converter level control can be exploited by the system level control. Especially for state estimation tasks a higher number of measurements available to the system level layer is beneficial. In addition to measurement data, control commands are transmitted on the system level layer. The converter level control receives current, voltage or power commands and executes them. This is achieved by an interface between both layers.

5.2 Converter Level

Converter level control comprises the current, voltage and power control loops of a converter as basic elements. As described in Section 3 and Section 4, certain sensors and communication within the converter are used depending on the requirements. The autonomous, standalone operation of the converter has to be ensured by this control layer. Therefore, during system design it has to be considered which converter operates under which control mode. The control gains and trajectory filters have to be set in a way that system stability is ensured by the converter level control layer. Therefore, a system analysis has to be carried out before its commissioning. In the layer based control approach it is mandatory that basic system stability does not depend on higher communication layers.

Simulations of a hybrid AC/DC system modelled after the RWTH demo site were performed to validate the developed converter level control layer's ability to ensure system stability. Figure 39 and Figure 40 show an overview of the system and the model that was simulated. One MV

and one LV AFE interface the system to the AC grid. The FEN DC grid connects similar to the real demo site the PGS test hall, including two 5 MW DAB converters, and the CWD. In this model the DC grid is interfaced to a DAB at the CWD side of the grid. An Input Series Output Parallel (ISOP) DAB consisting of eight modules interfaces the MV and LV part of the system. LVDC loads and generation units are modelled with two DABs connected to the LVDC bus.

During the simulation the AFEs, the modular DAB, as well as the two MV DABs at PGS test hall were running the developed voltage control. Both LVDC DABs and the DAB at CWD were in current control mode with a local set-point control to emulate loads and generation units. Figure 41, Figure 42 and Figure 43 show the key voltages and currents in the system during simulation. At the time $t = 0$ the CWD side of the grid sinks 200 A, the LVDC units source a total of 95 A. Shortly after that the power drawn by CWD is ramped down until power flow reverses and 200 A flow from CWD to PGS. It can be observed that all DC voltages in the system remain stable and are regulated within small windows. The inductive voltage drop across the lines of the FEN DC grid causes small deviations from the voltage reference during changes of the grid current. At the time instant $t = 0.23$ s the current set-point for one of the LV DABs is changed and its current ramps up accordingly. Overall, during all of the shown transients and stationary operating points the system remains stable. The converter level control layer can ensure system stability without any communication between converters or on system level.

Figure 39: Simplified schematic of the simulation model for the demo site.

Figure 40: View of the simulation model for the demo site.

Figure 41: FEN DC grid voltages and currents during simulation of system behavior under converter level control.

A control feature which improves system stability and acts on the converter level is droop control. Especially converters feeding an AC grid require a droop logic similar to that employed by classic synchronous generators in order to provide virtual inertia and control frequency and voltage of the AC grid. In DC grids droop control is used to allow power sharing of converters which are feeding the same bus and are operated under voltage control. Additionally, virtual damping to the system is introduced by the droop control. Figure 44 shows the schematic of

Figure 42: MV AFE DC link voltages during simulation of system behavior under converter level control.

Figure 43: LVDC voltage and currents during simulation of system behavior under converter level control.

a voltage control with droop logic. To the original voltage command v_{DCref} the term v_{droop} is added. v_{droop} depends on the output power of the converter and is the product of output current and droop factor k_{droop} according to Equation (14). In order to optimise the operation of multiple converters feeding the same DC bus the droop gains of each converter have to be negative. By adjusting the droop gains the ratio of power sharing between the converters is changed. In general, the droop coefficients have to be tuned depending on line inductances and capacitances in the system, in order to improve stability.

$$v_{droop} = i_{load} \cdot k_{droop} \tag{14}$$

Figure 44: Voltage control loop with droop logic.

The droop gains can be changed live, also by the converter level control. An example for this case is an AFE connected to a transformer substation on the AC side. If the transformer should only be loaded to a certain point the converter can autonomously adjust its droop gain to limit its share of the DC load. The other converters will react according to their voltage control loops and take over greater parts of the load. Additionally, higher control layers may act on the individual droop gains in order to optimise overall system behavior and operation.

Droop logic can also be used for the compensation of the voltage drop across a DC line instead of power sharing. The ohmic resistance of the corresponding line has to be estimated. For this use case k_{droop} is positive and equals the estimated resistance. Consequently, the output voltage at the converter terminals is adjusted in a way that the voltage at a given point of common coupling in the system is regulated. Variations of actual converter output voltage are within a similar small range as in the case of a negative droop coefficient. Figure 41 shows the effect of line compensation achieved by droop logic. The voltage V_{CWD} at the CWD side of the DC grid is regulated to be close to the nominal value during stationary operation by both DABs at PGS test hall. Therefore, the voltage at the PGS side of the grid is adjusted accordingly.

On the converter level layer the fault detection mechanisms of each converter are implemented. This is necessary to allow a fast and reliable response per converter during faults. Actions like fault ride through or shutdown of a converter have to work independently of the other communication layers.

5.3 Inter-Converter Level

The system performance and reliability can be further increased by addition of an inter-converter level control layer. Converters which are located in proximity to each other and share a common electrical connection to the system are connected through a communication link. An interface between the converter level control layer and the inter-converter level layer is required. Local sensors which are necessary for the operation of converter level control are exploited to implement control functions on the inter-converter level layer.

Power sharing of converters which are operated in parallel can also be implemented by means of a master-slave control. In this case one of the converters operates in voltage control mode and the parallel converters are operated in current control mode as slaves. The current command for the slave converters is given by the master converter. Different scenarios for power sharing are possible with this approach. However, it has to be ensured that the system remains stable in case of communication breakdown between the converters. A possible application

Figure 45: Online adjustment of droop coefficients.

for master slave control is visualised in Figure 1. Two DAB converters feed the FEN DC grid from PGS side. If one of the converters has a slower control response the power might not be shared equally between both converters, especially during transients. Here, both converters might be operated in voltage control mode with the addition of a master slave control which gives current set-points for the slave converter's current control. In case of a communication breakdown the slave converter can still operate under voltage control and system stability can be ensured.

A further application of inter-converter level control is the adjustment of droop coefficients and power or current set-points between converters for optimisation of operation. Additionally, in case of a fault converters which share a feeding or load bus can execute coordinated reactions and support each other during fault ride through.

Figure 45 shows a simulation of the LVDC part of the system in Figure 39. Modular DAB and LV AFE feed the LVDC bus, a prosumer unit is modelled by LV1DAB. At the beginning the prosumer unit feeds a current of 25A to the grid which is split equally between modular DAB and AFE. Their droop coefficients are 0.05 each. As soon as the prosumer unit ramps up its current at $t = 0.3$ s the droop coefficients of AFE and modular DAB are updated to 0.08 and 0.02 respectively. Accordingly, a change in the division of the load between AFE and modular DAB can be observed. Depending on the desired ratio of load sharing between the converters, the droop coefficients can be chosen accordingly.

6 Conclusions

Three control layers were defined based on the requirement of robust and stable system operation. The presented converter level control algorithms were implemented on down-scaled test setups and partly the full-size converters which are part of the RWTH demo site. Dynamic operation of the three phase DAB in normal grid conditions is enabled by the proposed control methods. Coupling of AC and DC grid parts can be realised based on the presented AFE control. Within simulations it has been verified that the converter level control layer is sufficient to ensure stable operation of the grid.

The presented converter level controls have to be implemented on all RWTH demo site converters in future work of WP7. Stability and function have to be verified by testing parts of the grid. Afterwards, tests of the complete system can be conducted. Furthermore, system level control algorithms have to be implemented and tested on the demo site hardware.

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